

The Environmental Impact of Industrialization and Sustainable Solutions

V. Praveen Kumar

Ph.D. Research Scholar (FT),
Kamaraj College, Thoothukudi.
Affiliated with Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.
9597032697, chillpraveenkumar@gmail.com

Dr. A. Devaraj

Head and Assistant Professor,
P.G. Research and Department of History,
Kamaraj College, Thoothukudi.
9894697387, saranyadevaraj2012@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Industrialization has brought economic prosperity; additionally, it has resulted in more population, urbanization, and apparent stress on the basic life-supporting systems while pushing the environmental impacts closer to the threshold tolerance limits. With booming industrial growth and relatively low land mass, ecological sustainability is now a significant deciding factor in industrial development. Accumulating evidence constantly indicates that the transition of the existing industries into the eco-industrial network through the successful implementation of green approaches provides a viable solution to preserve the region's natural resources while concurrently enhancing the regional economy on a sustainable basis. After carefully assessing past and prevailing conditions, it calls for an appropriate planning and integrated framework in harmony with the environment. The empirical knowledge of affected areas helps understand the local context and develop further courses of action based on ground realities. With this aim, a study was conducted on the current industrial pollution and environmental setting of Thoothukudi. A causal chain analysis indicated the severe impacts of industrialization on the local environment while highlighting its immediate and root causes.

Keywords: Industrialization, environment, sustainable solutions, Thoothukudi.

Introduction

Industrial growth has started to affect the environment for ages with severe downside problems. It causes tremendous stress on the entire network and natural system components like water, air, soil, and bio-diversity, including the surrounding ecosystem. Realizing the severity of the problem, the impacts of industrialization on the environment need to be analyzed with more intensity and feeling. Industrial effluents contain numerous essential nutrients or properties that can efficiently be utilized for many value-added purposes with commendable benefits to society and the environment. Application of green approaches based on 6Rs technologies (reduce, reuse, recycle, recovery, redesign, rethink) and closed-loop systems within the integrated framework of industrial ecology (IE) provides an excellent opportunity to preserve the natural resources of the region while concurrently enhancing the regional economy on a sustainable basis. It calls for appropriate strategic planning encompassing technical, ecological, socio-cultural and economic driving factors affecting industrialisation. Before evolving a practical approach towards strategic development, it will always be indispensable to derive lessons from similar situations. A systematic way of looking at events that occurred with identical consequences, critically analyzing the conditions, policies, activities and overall scenarios related to the problem, may help to gain a sharpened understanding of how the instance has happened. Against this backdrop, the industrial profile and impacts of industrialization on the environment were examined in Thoothukudi, which has emerged as an industrial nerve centre of South India over the past few years. Based on the lessons learned, this study indicates how a strategic green approach may be generated and applied in the Thoothukudi region and match the context in other parts of the world.

Industrial profile and local context of Thoothukudi

The pre-Independence period of the mid-1800s saw the first modern industries being set up along the coast; in 1854, the Bombay Spinning and Weaving Company was set up, followed by the Calcutta Jute Mill in 1855 (Chaloner, 1990). In Thoothukudi, the Madura Coats Cotton Mill was set up in 1877. During the post-Independence period, the Indian state followed a trajectory of development described as capital-intensive. Liberal development policies catalyzed the coal industry, which pioneered the iron and steel industry (Bansal, 1984). The expansion of the transport, communication and power networks was crucial in the

public sector. As the Indian power industry depends heavily on imported coal (ICC, 2012) and is water-intensive, thermal power plants gravitate towards coastal locations (Dharmadhikary, 2014). The coast soon became a hotspot for other import-export-based industries like chemicals and minerals. With industries and trade ushering in urbanization, today, three of India's four metro cities, with the country's largest populations, are located along the coast. By comparison, Thoothukudi has yet to emerge as a major metropolis, but the district remains an important industrial centre.

However, this form of industrial development has had severe consequences for coastal ecosystems comprising a diversity of habitats such as mangroves, swamps, tidal flats, beaches, dunes and coral reefs, supporting rich biodiversity. Such development has also been contested by various coastal communities whose livelihoods are based on these ecosystems. Several disasters have also cautioned against certain forms of development in coastal areas. With the spectre of climate change-induced sea level rise and associated weather events such as storms and cyclones awaiting us, it is believed that present-day development activities and their regulation will be crucial in determining the future of coast-based economies and societies.

Impacts of industrialization on Thoothukudi environment

Impacts on water and air

A detailed analysis of the environmental impacts of industrialization revealed that industries set up before the 1990s included mainly textiles, sugars and distilleries that were water-intensive and had a higher pollution potential, exerting enormous pressure on the environment. The indiscriminate discharge of industrial effluent, along and solid waste disposal, is the principal source of surface water contamination. The air quality is equally affected by industrialization.

Impacts on ecosystem

This uncontrolled industrialization brought changes in community and habitat structure. The forest cover of Thoothukudi has become significantly less, posing a threat to the current ecosystem. With this sudden boom in industries, the pattern of resource utilization in the form of energy, water usage etc., increased drastically, leading to the inevitable resource disturbance and imbalance. Today, the land bears no resemblance to its past except

in a few pockets of the region. It already affected the sedimentation patterns, the distribution of major and trace elements and the rate of soil formation, which brought significant changes in ecosystem stability. The regular inflow of industrial effluents into the ponds disturbed their ecological equilibrium.

Consequently, the water which previously could be used for domestic and agricultural purposes became exceedingly unusable. This, in turn, affected the cropping pattern. Though not conspicuously alarming, the slow and steady pollution by heavy metals in the environment is quite hazardous. They reach the aquatic environment and, being non-degradable, remains remained or are partially dissolved in water and subsequently in organisms.

Environmental Issues

Air Pollution is the primary environmental challenge faced by Thoothukudi, while water and noise pollution are environmental issues too. Thoothukudi is the only city from the state of Tamil Nadu to be listed as one of the Non-attainment cities by the Ministry of Environment primarily based on excess PM₁₀ under the National Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Program (NAMP) for the period 2011 - 2015. The city has many red industries, resulting in the PM₁₀ — tiny airborne particles seven times finer than human hair—exceeding national standards (60 micrograms per cubic metre, or $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) by around 200 per cent. Indian Standards for PM₁₀ are three times higher than WHO standards for PM₁₀ particles which are 20 micrograms per cubic metre. Environmentalists blame public and private coal-fired thermal power plants, copper smelters and chemical industries for polluting the air quality of Thoothukudi. A 2010 study published in the Journal of Eco Biotechnology cites Industrial pollution in Thoothukudi as a major cause of various health issues. Respondents of the study had various health issues like skin diseases, eye irritation, asthma, allergy, respiratory problems, cancer and hypertension. The study also observed that Industrial disposals and other chemical contaminants that enter waterways through agricultural runoff, storm water drains, and industrial discharges may persist in the environment for long periods and be transported by water or air over long distances. They disturb the function of the endocrine system, resulting in reproductive, developmental, and behavioural problems. The endocrine disrupters reduced fertility and increased the occurrence of stillbirths, congenital disabilities, and hormonally dependent Cancers such as breast, testicular, and prostate cancers. The

effects on the developing nervous system include impaired mental and psychomotor development, cognitive impairment and behavioural abnormalities. Studies like these led the people of Thoothukudi to protest the closing of the Sterlite plant in May 2018. On the 22nd of that month, the police opened fire on protestors killing 13 and injuring 102. The plant was soon closed.

Recommendations for Sustainable Solutions

Strategic planning is necessary to address the environmental impacts of economic development to an acceptable level. Eco-industrial network development provides viable solutions to sustainable industrialisation in a degrading environment and pressure for constant industrialization. However, it will require a supportive infrastructure base to make it happen. The industry will need a perfect combination of incentives, regulations, management mechanisms, information and other infrastructure facilities to provide the conditions where industrial symbiosis (IS) can thrive. A subsequent SWOT analysis by this author and her doctoral research broadly highlighted the significant potential for developing industrial clusters in different sectors in Thoothukudi. Potentials appear attractive for businesses looking into inter-organizational interfaces for by-products and resources. Five types (one-one, one-many, many-one, many-many and one-all) and 28 potential synergies were identified for by-product and resource exchanges during the same research. This can be supported by policy elements that emphasize and encourage the companies to move in directions aligned with IS principles. Regional development agencies and local Governments, which have increasingly accepted responsibility for balancing economic development with other pillars of sustainability, have a welcoming approach to the concept. Industrial diversity, continuous waste production, existing motivation in the work environment, the willingness of the govt., industry-friendly incentives/subsidies, massive investment in the industrial sector, good transport access, the proximity of industrial participants, and local academic skill/expertise provide promising opportunities for successful implementation of IE principles. All these create a supportive atmosphere for creating the eco-industrial park in this region based on material and by-product exchanges.

Conclusion

Rampant industrialization and urbanization have been fundamental causes for putting pressure on natural resources and also causing various degrees of environmental degradation.

Thoothukudi, the south Indian industrial base, has been experiencing a similar kind of situation for many decades. There is an urgent need for initiatives that ensure that industrialization is sustainable in terms of taking measures to prevent environmental damage and promoting more environmentally friendly industries. A transition of the industries into an eco-industrial network has emerged as a dynamic approach to preserve the natural region's natural resources. Strong linkages between industry and related services can accelerate this transition to a diversified, high-income economy while providing a safer environment. Situational analysis of the Thoothukudi region pointed to orevealedicant potential for industrial cluster development and inter-organizational interfaces for by-products and local resources. Key lessons learnt from Thoothukudi may be a reasonable basis for developing strategic action for areas with similar environmental problems. From a comprehensive analysis of local environmental settings, strategies can be evolved to overcome the problems by modifying or introducing appropriate approaches and filling the missing aspects of the related policies for strengthening sustainable industrialization.

Such solutions cannot be imposed from the outside and need a holistic approach widely understood or at least accommodated by local industrial systems. This will allow them to be readily absorbed into the local business culture while helping improve overall effectiveness, thereby assisting in a benign transformation of an existing 'business-as-usual culture' to a 'sustainability-based culture'. All that is needed to achieve this is a logical way to approach the strategy by binding all the essentials rooted in social, economic, environmental, technical, scientific, cultural and intellectual green components in an integrated fashion. Implementing a feasible green approach along these lines will create the much-desirable integrated structure needed to develop a sustainable industrial base in the regions with similar features.

Reference:

- [1] Azumi, D.S., and Bichi, M.H., (2010). Industrial pollution and heavy metals profile of Challawa River in Kano, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Science in Environmental Sanitation*. Vol.5(1), 23 - 293.
- [2] Banerjee, S.B., (1998). Corporate environmentalism: perspectives from organizational learning. *Management Learning*. 29, 147–64.
- [3] Barthwal, R.R., (2002). Environmental Impact Assessment. *Journal New Age*. p.11-12.2.
- [4] Chertow, M., (2000). Industrial symbiosis: literature and taxonomy. *Annual Review of Energy and Environment*. 25, 313–37.
- [5] Chiu, A.S.F., and Yong, G., (2004). On the industrial ecology potential in Asian developing countries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 12, 1037–45.
- [6] Clayton, A. et al. (2002). Enabling industrial symbiosis through a web-based waste exchange. *Greener Management International*. 40, 93–106.
- [7] <http://environmentinsider.com/impact-industrialization-environment/>
- [8] Madan, M., et.al. (2013). Harbour-Based Fisheries Management in Thoothukudi District - A Case of Thoothukudi Fishing Harbour. Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute. Pp. 361.
- [9] Madras Consultancy Group. 2008. Thoothukudi Vision -2025. CII (Confederation of Indian Industry).
- [10] Maria Queen Annes, D., & Sornaganesh, V. (2019). A study on the impact of industrialization in Thoothukudi. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*. Volume: 5, Issue: p. 7.